

Tellurium Salts of Certain Organic Acids

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Berzelius¹ observed that TeO_2 could be dissolved in tartaric acid forming a salt in which tellurium acted as a base. Becker² obtained tellurium acid tartrate, $\text{Te}(\text{HC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6)_4$, by spontaneous evaporation of a solution of TeO_2 in tartaric acid in air. Brauner³ found tellurium tetrabromide soluble in an aqueous solution of tartaric acid (1:1), forming an orange-yellow solution, which could be diluted with water without separation of tellurous acid owing to the formation of tellurium tartrate. The formation of tellurium acid tartrate was later confirmed by Hageman⁴ who also prepared a white, crystalline tellurium acid citrate, $\text{Te}(\text{HC}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7)_2$, by dissolving TeO_2 in citric acid and subsequent heating for a month. Rosenheim and Weinheber⁵ prepared telluric acid oxalate, $\text{R}_2(\text{H}_6\text{TeO}_6 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$, by adding H_6TeO_6 to an aqueous solution of alkali oxalate.

In the present investigation TeCl_4 has been treated with free organic acids to form the corresponding salts of tellurium.

Tellurium tetrachloride was prepared from its constituent elements and purified by distillation. The other chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E. Merck's 'extra pure' quality. The acids were recrystallised and dehydrated before use.

A slight excess of the acid was added to a solution of tellurium tetrachloride in benzene and mixed well in a reaction vessel, connected to CaCl_2 and P_2O_5 tubes. The mixture was slowly warmed at $60-70^\circ$ on a sand bath for 4 hours. The temperature was then slowly raised to $10-15^\circ$ higher than the melting point of the acid and the mixture heated till the evolution of HCl gas had ceased; but in the case of higher fatty acids, the mixture was heated between 60° and 80° for few days. The product was cooled and washed with some suitable organic solvents till free of the excess of the acid. It was dried and analysed.

Slight decomposition was observed during formation of the compounds obtained with myristic, palmitic, adipic, succinic, and phthalic acids, but no decomposition in other cases.

1. *Pog. Ann.*, 1826, 8, 411.

2. *Annalen*, 1876, 180, 257.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1889, 55, 382.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 342.

5. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1911, 69, 281.

Tellurium was weighed as TeO_2 ; carbon and hydrogen were estimated in a few cases by combustion method.

In all the cases the compounds obtained are crystalline, slightly hygroscopic but fairly stable under normal conditions. They are generally soluble in ethanol, acetone or ethyl acetate, but insoluble in ether, chloroform, or CCl_4 . The compounds obtained with lauric, myristic, palmitic, stearic, and benzoic acids are fairly soluble in hot benzene and sparingly in CCl_4 . These are slowly decomposed by hot water, acids, and alkalis.

TABLE I

Acids.	Products.	Colour.	% Tellurium.	
			Found.	Reqd.
A. Tellurium (IV) chloride with monocarboxylic acids. TeCl_4 : acid=1:4.				
Lauric	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{COO}]_4\text{Te}$	Yellowish brown	13.77	13.32
Myristic	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{12}\text{COO}]_4\text{Te}$	Grey	12.30	12.32
Palmitic	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{14}\text{COO}]_4\text{Te}$	Dirty yellow	11.20	11.12
Stearic	$[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{16}\text{COO}]_4\text{Te}$	Light brown	10.16	10.13
Benzoic	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}]_4\text{Te}$	"	20.78	20.86
B. Tellurium (IV) chloride with dicarboxylic acids. TeCl_4 :acid=1:2.				
Succinic	$\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \end{array} \right]_2\text{Te}$	White	35.51	35.48
Adipic	$[(\text{CH}_2)_4(\text{COO})_2]_2\text{Te}$	"	30.75	30.70
Sebacic	$[(\text{CH}_2)_8(\text{COO})_2]_2\text{Te}$	Dirty white	24.23	24.18
Phthalic	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{COO})_2]_2\text{Te}$	Grey	27.89	28.01
C. Tellurium (IV) chloride with hydroxy-acids.				
Salicylic	$[\text{OH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO}]_4\text{Te}$	White	18.62	18.88
Gallie	$[(\text{OH})_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{COO}]_4\text{Te}$	Light yellow	15.91	15.88
Tannic	$[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{O}_9]_2\text{Te}$	Brownish black	16.38	16.62
Malic	$[\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})(\text{COO})_2]_2\text{Te}$	Dark brown	33.28	33.26

One molecule of TeCl_4 reacts with four molecules of monobasic acids and two molecules of dibasic acids. With dibasic acids the reaction is comparatively fast and requires shorter duration for completion. In the case of hydroxy-acids the H of the hydroxyl group is not replaced.

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